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ABSTRACTS

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COASTAL MANAGEMENT, NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS, ENVIRONMENT

EFFECTIVENESS OF SAND TRAPS IN PROMOTING SEDIMENT GAIN IN FOREDUNES OF A SEMI-NATURAL BEACH (COSTA BRAVA, SPAIN)

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INTRODUCTION:

Foredunes are natural barriers that protect coastal areas from erosion and flooding. However, they are under threat worldwide due to climate change, rising sea levels, and human activities. In Catalonia, the degradation of the dune landscape is estimated to be 90%, mainly due to urbanization and its impact on beach-dune systems (Garcia-Lozano et al., 2018). Human impacts are the primary cause of dune degradation on the low-lying coast of Costa Brava, being the implementation of nature-based solutions a successful tool to restore dune morphologies. This study evaluates the effectiveness of sand traps in promoting sediment gain in the foredunes of a semi-natural beach in Costa Brava, two years after their implementation.

METHODOLOGY:

Digital elevation models were retrieved from UAV data collected over two years, before and after the implementation of sand traps on el Riuet Beach. The data was processed using PIX4Dmapper software to obtain digital elevation models with resolutions of 15 cm. The study area is a 4 ha semi-natural beach surrounded by croplands and included in a Natural Park. The MAVIC DJI was used for flight, and the two flights compared were from the summer of 2019 and winter of 2023 (before the storm period).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The implementation of sand traps led to a significant increase in sediment gain in the foredune area, with an average height increase of one meter, or 46%, from 2.8 to 3.8 meters above sea level. The sand traps effectively trapped sand and prevented it from being carried away by winter storms, allowing the beach-dune profile slope to recover. The zone surrounding the sand traps has been located at a maximum height of 4 m since its implementation in the winter of 2020-2021. Cordoned dunes have also considerably reduced human trampling, although cruising practices still occur. Sexual human niches are now the main cause of foredune treatment in the study area, being the main cause of dune deflation and reactivation of blowouts by means of unmanaged pathways.

The increasing demand for sustainable beach management has sparked a growing scientific and engineering interest in exploring how natural processes can provide solutions to address the degradation and vulnerability of beaches and dunes (Slinger et al., 2021). However, cruising is known to be a significant cause of dune degradation and human frequency, even when nature-based solution are implemented (García-Romero et al., 2022). While cordoned dunes may deter users with sand beach tourism, it may not be sufficient for cruising tourism. Additional measures, such as surveillance and fines, are necessary to prevent cordoned-off dunes from

being crossed.

Figure 1 - Foredune evolution of Riuet Beach before (2019) and after (2023) nature-based solutions were implemented to restore dune systems.

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